

S1 Table. Schedule of the Brazilian Python Workshop for Biological Data in 2021.

Time	Day 1	Day 2	Day 3	Day 4	Day 5
8h30	Welcome	Presentation: Introduction to Pandas and Matplotlib	Reserved for group and individual Exercises, questions and answers	Presentation: Results obtained in the group exercises	Presentation: Problem of the Day
9h00	Live Coding - Introduction to Python and its data structures	Live Coding – Introduction to Tabulated Data Manipulation		Live Coding – Exploration of epidemiological data	Live Coding - Exploration of biological diversity data
10h00					
10h30					
11h00					
12h00	Break			Break	
13h00	Talk: MitoHifi – finding and annotating circular molecules	Talk: Machine learning applied to biological issues		Talk: Analysis of biological networks in Python	Talk: Best practices and reproducibility of Python scripts
14h00	Live Coding - Introduction to Python and its data structures	Live Coding – Graphical Exploratory Data Analysis		Live Coding – Exploration of epidemiological data	Flash Talks - Participants Projects
15h00					Live Coding - Exploration of biological diversity data
16h00					
17h00 - 18h00	Questions and Answers		Questions and Answers	Workshop Closure	